

Online Learning Platforms on Academic Performance: A Study in Kebbi State's Public Schools

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The increasing integration of digital technologies in education has brought about a very significant change in teaching and learning process, particularly through the usage of the online learning platforms. This shift has become more prominent in response to disruptions such as the COVID-19 pandemic. Despite their growing adoption, there are still debate on the effectiveness of these platforms in enhancing academic performance, especially in public secondary schools that mostly face the issue of resource constraints. This study, hence, intend to investigates the impact of online learning platforms on students' academic performance in some selected public secondary schools in Kebbi State. It explores the key factors influencing this relationship, including the student engagement, their access to technology, teacher's preparedness, and parental guidance. By employing a mixed-methods approach which combines quantitative analysis of academic records with qualitative data from surveys and interviews, the research aims to identify both the challenges and opportunities associated with online learning in resource-limited environments. Our findings discovered that though online learning platforms are extensively used and agreed to improve access to educational resources and student engagement, financial and infrastructural challenges prevent them from reaching their full potential.

Keywords:
Online Learning,
Academic
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Public,
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Educational
Technology,
Student Engagement

Introduction

The rapid integration of digital technology has led to a significant revolution in education at the start of the 21st century. In particular, online learning platforms have become an important teaching and learning tools because they provide new methods to acquire educational content, make collaboration easier, and allow for more individualized training (Josué, Bedoya-Flores, Mosquera-Quíñonez, Mesías-Simisterra, & Bautista-Sánchez, 2023). The COVID-19 pandemic, which forced a transition to distant learning and brought attention to the advantages and disadvantages

of digital education, hastened this global change (Shestakova, Morgunov, Novikova, & Bylieva, 2025). The effectiveness of these platforms in actually improving academic achievement is still up for discussion, despite their widespread acceptance, particularly in public educational systems that usually struggle with resource constraints.

Public secondary schools in Nigeria and many other developing nations mostly face challenges, such as the uneven access to technology, poor infrastructure, and lack of teacher preparation (Mohammed, Ogunode, & Yahaya, 2021). These challenges can greatly hinder the effective execution of

activities concerning the online learning. Therefore, it is very important to understand how the platforms works in these kinds of environment and how they affect student performances.

Furthermore, there are still debates on how well online learning environments might raise student achievement, particularly in public secondary schools in areas with very limited funding (Topping, Douglas, Robertson, & Ferguson, 2022). Numerous public schools in Kebbi State deal with serious issues such as restricted access to internet enabled devices, erratic connection settings, instructors' lack of digital literacy, and low parental support. The effectiveness and impact of online learning may be hampered by these characteristics, which begs the question of whether these platforms actually improve students' academic achievement in these kinds of settings.

This study addresses the debate around the efficacy of online learning platforms in public secondary schools in Kebbi State, Nigeria, amid challenges such as resource constraints, influence of the platforms on the academic achievement of students. The study will examine critical impacting elements including student engagement, technological access, teacher readiness, and parental participation, while also recognizing difficulties and opportunities in resource-constrained environments. The findings offer insights on enhancing the design and execution of online learning initiatives for educators, administrators, and policymakers. These are achieved through: evaluating the level of access and utilization of online learning platforms by students and educators in the selected public secondary schools, analyzing how students' use of online resources affects their academic performance

and determine the main obstacles preventing efficient usage of online learning platforms in educational settings with low resources.

The remaining of the paper is divided into four (4), which include review of related literature, methodology, findings and discussion, and conclusion and recommendations.

Review of Related Literature

In this session, the review of different related literature from previous studies showing mixed results on the impact of online learning on academic performance with infrastructure and students engagement as key factors are been discussed.

(Rodgers, 2008) present a study that examines the impact on end-of-year examination grades of the level of student engagement in the e-learning process. A mixture of traditional lectures and e-learning based methods were used to examines the data for the presence of interaction effects between e-learning engagement and personal characteristics. And the result shows that female students benefited less from e-learning material than their male counterparts.

(Zen & Ariani, 2022) analyzes the effect of Project-Based Online Learning (PBOL) and student engagement on academic achievement. The study utilized a mixed-method of data collection using quantitative through interviews, observations and documentation and qualitative method through questioners and portfolios. The result shows that students' perception of implementing the PBOL method and student engagement increased their academic performance to become new entrepreneurs through the experience they gained during project-based learning. However, the method

only provides online learning solution for entrepreneurship courses.

(Galal, Vyas, Ndung'u, Wu, & Webber, 2023) examines student engagement with weekly self-paced learning materials in a virtual therapeutics course, and how sub-factors in the Motivated Strategies for Learning Questionnaire (MSLQ) may have influenced academic performance. Various correlation analyses were used to determine the predictive ability of the MSLQ. The result proved the MSLQ to be an effective predictive tool in students' self-regulation skills.

(Sahni, 2023) assesses the levels of student engagement in the online learning environment, examine how student engagement is related to their academic performance using learning analytic tools and propose an integrated learning analytics framework. Exploratory research method was used for data collection from different sources including LMS Logs, self-administered questionnaires from students, and interviews with the instructors. The study provides new perception that student engagement is the key to their participation and performance in online courses and also confirms that LMS and learning analytics can be powerful tools to support predictions on student performances.

(Ihebom & Uko, 2020) outlined the goals of secondary education in Nigeria and highlighted their challenges as; poor funding, lack of qualified teachers, poor infrastructure, lack of motivation of teachers, overcrowded classrooms, poor management and supervision, dilapidated/obsolete school facilities and equipment, improper placement of teachers, poor research mindedness of teachers, lack of professional training, and

teacher's poor knowledge of ICT. The study suggested that the federal and state government, policy makers in education, schools board must work in synergy to see that the anomalies are taken care of. Also, private sector and other non-governmental bodies like NGO's should be incorporated. Furthermore, more practical skills like the use of computer, creativity and other vocational skills should be considered in measuring the learning performance of students.

(Abuhassna et al., 2020) investigates the potential factors influencing students' academic achievements and satisfaction using online learning platforms. The study was conducted using online learning platforms in higher education. A quantitative research method was utilized for the study and eleven factors were discussed on using online learning platforms to improve students' academic achievements and satisfaction. It shows that hat the students' background, experience, collaborations, interactions, and autonomy positively affected students' satisfaction. Furthermore, the empirical findings present a strong support to the integrative association between TDT and BTT theories in relation to using online learning platforms in improving students' academic achievements and satisfaction.

(Batool, Mehrukh, & Waseem, 2023) evaluates online and traditional learning for effectiveness and student satisfaction. A quantitative approach was used for the data collection considering Age, gender, and major. Two questionnaires were administered in assessing the student satisfaction and performance using both online learning platforms and traditional classrooms. Most students mentioned that

online and traditional classrooms were beneficial. While others said online learning platforms were better at facilitating self-paced learning, tailored instruction, and a wide selection of learning materials.

(Juty, 2024) investigates the influence of e-learning platforms in promoting academic efficiency among Bangladeshi rural students. A paper-based questionnaire on educational ICT and the e-learning experience was utilized. The study also uses a mixed method through a survey and interview to determine how the online learning platform are being utilized, its impact, and the challenges the organization might have faced. And the result shows that every rural school in Bangladesh makes use of online learning resources.

(Wanyonyi, 2022) assess the impact of virtual learning and teaching platforms on the academic performance of high school students taking international curriculum. Research question was administered in the research. The study utilizes a descriptive survey design in obtaining responses from the respondents. The study found that on the average, 60% of students agreed that virtual learning improves the accessibility of education while 15.5% disagreed. It was concluded that there is a challenge of accessing alternative materials with the traditional mode of education delivery which necessitated the need to implement virtual learning.

(Clark, Nong, Zhu, & Zhu, 2021) estimates the causal effects of online education on student exam performance. Difference-in-differences approach was employed showing that online education during the COVID-19 lockdown improved student academic results by 0.22 of a standard deviation, relative to pupils without learning support from their

school. The study also shows that students who were given recorded online lessons from external higher-quality teachers had higher exam scores than those whose lessons were recorded by teachers from their own school.

(Jabbar Alkubaisi, Al-Saifi, Al-Shidi, & Al-Shukaili, 2021) identify the quality of online learning platforms, applying a set of criteria from the perspective of faculty members and students in higher education institutions in the Sultanate of Oman. A descriptive approach was employed and the data was collected through a questionnaire directed at 32 faculty members and 104 students. And the results show that e-learning programs are generally of high quality, from the perspective of the participants, but with statistically significant differences according to the type of program.

(Rakic, Pavlovic, Softic, Lalic, & Marjanovic, 2019) explores the evaluation of student success at e-learning platform. A multi-method approach for data analysis was employed in making the evaluation. The approach provides more detailed analysis that enable more relevant results showing that digital resources at the e-learning platform make strong effects on student success. Moreover, results indicate that students with the similar grades belongs to the same clusters.

(Hadiana, Wardhani, Muhsinin, Mursyidi, & Mubarak, 2024) investigate how online learning platforms, including education methods, and teacher professional development affect student outcomes. A literature review methodology was employed covering findings from academic articles, industry reports, case studies, and empirical studies to provide an insight of the current state of knowledge in this field. The findings

show that online learning platforms, when appropriately utilized, they offer individualized and flexible learning experiences that can boost student participation and achievement.

(Venugopal, 2024) highlight the impact of digital learning platforms on student engagement and academic performance. The study utilizes a mixed-methods approach, including quantitative analysis of student performance data and qualitative approach gathered through interviews. The result shows a significant positive impact between the use of digital learning platforms, student engagement and academic achievement. However, challenges such as technological barriers and pedagogical implementation issues are also discovered. Overall, the results underline the significance of successful integration techniques while highlighting the potential of digital learning platforms to improve educational outcomes.

Research Methodology

Kebbi State is located between latitudes 100 and 130N and longitudes 30 and 60E in the northwest in Nigeria. Farmland makes up 36.46% of the entire land area, which is around 37,699 square kilometers. Several secondary schools are in Kebbi State from which some were used from different local governments for this research. This study will investigate the impact of online learning platforms on the academic performance of students in designated public secondary institutions in Kebbi State, Nigeria. Student engagement, technological accessibility, teacher preparedness, and parental involvement, will be examined while also recognizing the difficulties and prospects

associated with resource-limited settings. A mixed-method approach is employed using a structured questionnaire distributed via social media platforms, analyzed using SPSS version 27 to identify patterns in online learning platform usage and its impact. The link to the questionnaire is <https://forms.gle/VftDZ7scSjQmCysEA>.

The population of the study consisted of teachers from different levels and students from different classes.

Data Analysis

A total number of one hundred and thirty-three (133) responses were obtained from both the students and teachers from which 65.9% of them were male and 34.1% female. Getting (62.2%) students and (37.8%) teachers. The analysis revealed that 82.8% of the respondents had personal access to online learning devices, with a majority utilizing smartphones, indicating a high level of digital engagement among teachers and students.

Result

Usage and platforms preference

The responses highlight how often online platforms are used from the various schools and which ones are most popular. And the most popular platform is WhatsApp groups getting a (51.5%), followed by Google Classroom (38.1%). Microsoft Teams was also used by (4.5%) of respondents. Other platforms were used by a few number of people having a percentage of (5.9%).

Usage And Respective Percentage

Frequency of Use	Percentage (%)
Several times in a week	19.3%
Rarely	34.1%
Daily	33.3%
Once in a week	11.1%
Other	2.2%

Perception and Challenges

This section summarizes the opinions on how online learning platforms have impacted education and the main challenges encountered. The tables below show the

respondents responses on their perceptions and the challenges faced with the online learning.

Educational Resources Access

Access to Educational Resources	Percentage (%)
Strongly Agreed	41.5%
Agreed	38.5%
Neutral	12.6%
Disagree	6.3%
Strongly disagreed	1.1%

Engagement With the Online Learning

Engagement with Online Lessons	Percentage (%)
Strongly Agreed	43.7%
Agreed	34.8%
Neutral	16.3%
Disagree	5.2%
Strongly disagreed	0.0%

Online learning platforms used

The above bar chart shows the online learning platforms used by the respondents with a majority using WhatsApp groups.

Challenges Faced With The Online Learning

The result shows that most of the challenges faced were poor internet connection, lack of devices, high cost of internet data and power supply issue.

Conclusion

This study examined the influence of online learning platforms on students' academic achievement in the selected public secondary schools in Kebbi State. The results demonstrate that while tools like WhatsApp and Google Classroom are extensively utilized and regarded to improve resource accessibility and lesson interaction, their efficacy is limited by socio-economic and infrastructure issues. The most significant obstacles were identified as inadequate access to digital devices, high data charges, poor internet connectivity, and unstable electricity.

Our study confirms the positive impact of online learning platforms on academic performance in Kebbi State's public schools with majority of respondents feeling that the platforms have improved their access to more educational materials and increased their interest in online courses, highlighting the need for policies to improve access to

technology and engage stakeholders in the educational process.

The study suggests focused interventions to overcome the issues mentioned above and optimize the advantages of online learning. First, by making investments in digital infrastructure and offer reasonably priced internet access. Second, guarantee efficient use of platforms, teacher capacity building in digital pedagogy had to be given top priority. Third, to encourage the long-term integration of blended and online learning models, administrative and policy frameworks need to be reinforced.

Although, this study offers insightful details about how online learning environments affect students' academic achievement in the selected public secondary schools in Kebbi State, it also creates some numerous opportunities for more research. In future research, tools for resource-constrained contexts can be determine to assess the efficacy of particular platforms like Moodle,

Microsoft Teams, Google Classroom, and WhatsApp by employing a comparison approach. In a similar fashion, longitudinal research is advised to evaluate the long-term effects of online learning environments on skill acquisition, retention, and academic performance.

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